

SIEBERT, R.

Policy Brief: Soil Policy Begins with Perception – Why a New Framing is Key to Transformative Governance

Despite their central ecological role, soils are often perceived in political and institutional discourses as passive, inert, and under-theorized substrates. This perception manifests itself in their relative neglect in environmental governance compared to other resources such as air and water (Bouma, 2010; Ronchi et al., 2019). Rather than being recognized as dynamic, multifunctional systems that form the basis of almost all terrestrial life, soils are frequently treated as technocratic entities – as resources that need to be optimized, measured and managed with little regard for their socio-cultural, historical or ethical dimensions (Baveye et al., 2016).

The concept of framing refers to the ways in which issues are selectively presented and interpreted through particular narratives and categories, which in turn shape public understanding, political priorities and institutional responses (Hajer & Versteeg, 2005). In the context of soil governance, framing matters because it determines which aspects of soil are made visible or invisible in discourse and policy. It influences which stakeholders are considered relevant, what knowledge is valued, and how responsibility is assigned. A narrow, technocratic framing can exclude local knowledge, ethical concerns and relational dimensions of soil stewardship, while a broader, more inclusive framing can support democratic legitimacy, contextual sensitivity and more robust governance arrangements. The challenge is therefore not only technical or institutional in nature, but also discursive: How can soil be communicated and valued in ways that reflect its ecological complexity, socio-cultural relevance and foundational role for sustainable development?

WHY SOIL SECURITY AND SOIL HEALTH ARE NOT SUFFICIENT AS FRAMING: THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL LIMITATIONS

The concept of Soil Security, introduced by McBratney et al. (2014), was an important step towards improving the political visibility of soils. It outlines five dimensions – capacity, condition, capital, connectivity and codification – that aim to convey the contribution of soils to important societal goals such as food production, climate regulation and biodiversity conservation. This framing has increasingly proven effective in social science studies, as it aligns with global policy discourses on ecosystem services and sustainability metrics. The social science debate tends to favour the concept of ‘soil security’ because it comprehensively captures the critical socio-economic, political and governance-related dimensions of soils. In contrast, the natural science discourse focuses more on measurable parameters of ‘soil health’ in order to investigate biophysical laws. These different conceptualisations thus reflect fundamentally different disciplinary interests.

However, critics have highlighted fundamental weaknesses. Baveye et al. (2016) caution that the soil security approach risks reducing soils to mere service providers, ignoring their complex biogeochemical dynamics and site-specific ecologies. The framing of soil health, on the other hand, tends to reduce soils to their measurable functions, potentially obscuring essential cultural, aesthetic and relational values. Vogel et al. (2021) also show that such reductionism limits our ability to manage soils as dynamic systems. Paul et al. (2021) argue that this framing promotes technocratic, top-down policy instruments, while marginalizing qualitative, normative and cultural dimensions of soil management.

These theoretical concerns are supported by empirical research. Using an agent-based modelling approach, Kaim et al. (2025) found that fertiliser regulations lead to different outcomes depending on local conditions and farmers' behaviour patterns. This means that uniform policy instruments can lead to unintended or counterproductive effects, underscoring the importance of context sensitivity. Similarly, a governance study by Bartkowski et al. (2021) shows that existing policy frameworks often lack mechanisms for recognising non-instrumental soil values, and implementation is frequently reduced to symbolic gestures. These findings reinforce the conclusion that soil policy must not only be based on technical standards and indicators, but also on dialogue, mutual understanding and appreciation of local knowledge.

THE SOIL APPRECIATION FRAME AND ITS POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The Soil Appreciation Frame offers a transformative alternative by recognizing soils not only as providers of ecosystem services, but as living, relational entities embedded in ecological, cultural and social systems (Kenter et al., 2015). This framing, which is adopted by the EU Soil Mission in projects such as SoilScape and taken into account in its communications, shifts the focus from technical control and measurement to recognition, dialogue and co-creation. It promotes a holistic understanding of soil that incorporates ethical responsibilities, local values and the diverse relationships people have with the land. Instead of asking what soils can do for us, it invites us to reflect on how we live with and through soils. This reorientation has significant implications for governance. It supports inclusive policy processes, promotes long-term management and is consistent with contemporary governance paradigms that emphasise value pluralism and participatory knowledge production (Hajer & Versteeg, 2005). To put this change into practice, policy must actively incorporate communication, culture and context.

Governments, research institutions and civil society should reshape the representation of soils in public discourse and education. Instead of relying solely

on technical terms and environmental functions, communication should emphasise the emotional, historical and cultural dimensions of soils. Public campaigns, curricula and cultural media must tell compelling stories that promote identification with the soil and its care. Schools and scientific centres should incorporate narratives about the soil that connect learners with local landscapes and their hidden foundations. Soil monitoring systems must evolve beyond purely biophysical indicators. They should incorporate qualitative, participatory metrics that capture how soils are perceived and valued in different contexts. These could include farmer-led observations, community soil walks and participatory mapping initiatives that reflect both soil condition and social significance (Paul et al., 2021).

Legal frameworks at national and international levels should explicitly recognize soils as cultural and common goods. This means that laws must be developed that not only protect soils from degradation, but also support their role as heritage, memory and identity (Ronchi et al., 2019). Effective soil policy further requires genuine co-governance structures that empower local actors. Multi-actor platforms at regional level should be equipped with decision-making authority, access to data and resources for promotion. These structures should bring together farmers, scientists, planners and communities to jointly develop soil strategies. Participation must go beyond consultation — it must be institutionalized and empowering (Bartkowski et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION: REFRAMING SOIL AS A CULTURAL AND POLITICAL SUBJECT

The adoption of the 2025 EU Soil Monitoring Law could be an important step towards a more robust soil policy in Europe. Yet legal obligations alone will not suffice. What is needed is not only a refinement of policy instruments, but a paradigmatic shift in how soil is perceived, narrated and governed. The Soil Appreciation Frame demonstrates that soils are not only environmental resources, but also constitutive elements of our cultural and social worlds. This understanding invites a broader reflection on the conditions under which policy becomes meaningful, effective and just.

From a social science perspective, the reframing of soil offers a powerful entry point into broader questions of relational governance, value pluralism and democratic legitimacy. It challenges dominant narratives of control and optimization and instead promotes ideas of reciprocity, care and co-production. Governance, in this view, becomes a cultural practice – shaped by how we talk about soil, who is invited to the conversation and what values are made visible (Hajer & Versteeg, 2005). By focusing on appreciation rather than utility, the Soil Appreciation Frame promotes policies that are not only more inclusive but also better reflect the real complexity of soil-related decisions.

To achieve this, soil policy must draw on instruments that are capable of dealing with complexity, ambiguity and diversity. These include experimental and deliberative policy designs, participatory processes and transdisciplinary research approaches. Above all, it requires a willingness to view soil not as an object of governance, but as part of it – as a living medium that connects ecology, memory, identity and justice. The Soil Appreciation Frame, while still in development, provides the discursive and institutional foundation for this shift. Its success will depend on our collective ability to tell different stories, form new alliances and take seriously the ethical and cultural dimensions of life in and with the soil.

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Contact: bartosz.bartkowski@ufz.de